

Electrometric Study on Cu(II), Hg(II) and Ag(I) Complexes of Ethane-1,2-Dithiol and Determination of Their Solubility Products

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Cu(II), Hg(II) and Ag(I) complexes of Ethane-1,2-dithiol have been studied in 25% ethanol by employing potentiometric, conductometric and amperometric titration techniques. Whereas 1 : 1 complex is formed with Cu(II) and Hg(II), Ag(I) shows the formation of 2 : 1 complex. Equilibrium constants and solubility products of these complexes have been evaluated by Ringbom's method at 25°, 35° and 45°. The changes in the thermodynamic parameters ΔG , ΔH and ΔS , accompanying complexation reactions have also been reported.

THIOLS, containing an active -SH group, have a wide range of applications in biological, pharmaceutical, industrial and other chemical fields and are well known for their tendency to form complexes with metals. Several metal complexes of thiols have already been studied by Saxena and co-workers¹⁻⁴. The present communication reports the composition of sparingly soluble complexes of Cu(II), Hg(II) and Ag(I) with Ethane-1, 2-dithiol by amperometric, conductometric and potentiometric methods.

Experimental

Ethane-1, 2-dithiol (referred to herein as EDT) and other chemicals were used of Analar (B.D.H.) quality. Freshly prepared solutions were used to avoid the effects of ageing and air oxidation.

Potentiometric and conductometric titrations, both direct and reverse, were performed using a Cambridge bench pH meter and an electronic eye type conductometer. Similar concentrations of reactants were employed for both these titrations; in direct cases, the metal ion had the concentration 2 mM, 1 mM, 0.5 mM and [EDT] was 20 mM and in the reverse case, metal ion concentration was taken as 100 mM and [EDT] 4 mM, 8 mM, 12 mM. 25 ml of the titre solution in 25% ethanol was used in each case and the end points corresponding to the complex formation were obtained from the breaks in the titration curves.

Amperometric titrations were performed in an inert atmosphere of nitrogen using a manual polarograph with scalamp galvanometer as current recorder and S.C.E. as reference electrode. The capillary had the following characteristics in 25% ethanol, 0.1 M NaClO₄ and 0.002% Triton X-100 at -0.5 V vs. S.C.E. with h_{eff} value being 38.3 cm., $m = 2.963$ mg/sec, $t = 2.39$ sec. 25 ml solution of the titre in

25% ethanol contained 2 mM metal ion, 0.1 M NaClO₄ and 0.002% Triton X-100 and the concentration of the titrant used was 20 mM EDT in ethanol.

Results and Discussion

As reported earlier⁵, ethane-1, 2-dithiol produces diffusion controlled anodic wave associated with a prewave at d.m.e. It is observed that at -0.7 V vs. S.C.E., the metals under investigation are reducible but EDT shows inert behaviour. Hence amperometric titrations at -0.7 V were carried out in 25% ethanol, 0.1 M NaClO₄ and 0.002% Triton X-100 for determining the composition, equilibrium constants and solubility products of the complexes.

Stoichiometry: For establishing the stoichiometry of the complex species formed during the interaction of metal ion and EDT, a series of conductometric, potentiometric and amperometric titrations were carried out using different concentrations of reactants both by direct and reverse methods (Fig. 1). The equivalence points in the titrations curves corresponded to the formation of 1 : 1 complex for Cu(II) and Hg(II) and 2 : 1 for Ag(I).

Equilibrium Constants and solubility products: The values of equilibrium constants for the complexation reactions between metal ion and the ligand have been determined by Ringbom's method⁶. The following equation⁷ has been used for evaluating K_t , the conditional or formal equilibrium constant.

$$\frac{(i - i_r)(1 + rf)}{(i^0 - i_r)} = \frac{(1 - f) + [(1 - f)^2 + 4(1 + rf)^2 / K_t(C^0_M)^2]^{\frac{1}{2}}}{2} \quad \dots (1)$$

where r is the dilution parameter ($r = \frac{C^0_M}{C_x}$) and

Fig. 1. Curves 1, 2, 3-Conductometric titrations of 25 ml solution containing 2 mM Hg²⁺, Cu²⁺, Ag⁺ respectively against 20 mMED.T. Curves 4, 5, 6-Conductometric titrations of 25 ml solution containing 4 mM EDT against 100 mM Hg²⁺, Cu²⁺, Ag⁺ respectively.

f is the titration parameter defined by the equation

$$f = Z \frac{V_x C_x}{V^0 M C^0_M} \quad \dots (2)$$

Z being the number of moles of the titre which react with each mole of the titrant; in the present case *Z* = 1 for Cu(II) and Hg(II) and 2 for Ag(I). *C*⁰_{*M*} and *i*⁰ are the initial concentration and limiting current of the metal ion respectively; *i*_{*r*} and *i* are respectively the residual current and the current at any titration point. The titration parameter *f* becomes equal to unity at the equivalence point.

When a reducible ion is titrated with an inert one to give a precipitate, equation (1) at the equivalence point can be written as

$$K_t = \left(\frac{1}{C^0_M} \times \frac{i^0 - i_r}{i - i_r} \right)^2 \quad \dots (3)$$

from which the value of *K_t* under the conditions of the titration can be obtained. The value of $\frac{i^0 - i_r}{i - i_r}$ at the equivalence point was obtained from the plot of

$$\frac{i - i_r}{i^0 - i_r} \times \frac{V_0 + v}{V_0} \text{ vs. } f \text{ (Fig. 2).}$$

In the absence of any side reaction that could consume either ion, *K_t* for the precipitation titration is simply the reciprocal of the solubility product, *K_s*. Thus from the value of *K_t*, *K_s* for Cu(II), Hg(II) and Ag(I) complexes may also be evaluated.

The values of *K_t* and *K_s* for Cu(II), Hg(II) and Ag(I) complexes of Ethane-1, 2-dithiol at 25°, 35° and 45° are given in Table 1.

Thermodynamic functions: The values of changes in the free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS), accompanying the complexation reactions have been determined at 35° with the help of standard,

Fig. 2. Curves 1, 2, 3-Plot of $\frac{i - i_r}{i^0 - i_r} \frac{V_0 + v}{V_0}$ vs. *f* for Cu²⁺, Ag⁺, Hg²⁺ respectively at 25°.

TABLE 1

Values of *K_t* and *K_s* for Cu(II), Hg(II) and Ag(I) complexes of ethane-1, 2-dithiol.

Complex	Equilibrium constant (<i>K_t</i>) × 10 ⁻⁷			Solubility product (<i>K_s</i>) × 10 ⁶		
	25°	35°	45°	25°	35°	45°
Cu(II)	2.074	1.345	0.990	4.821	7.437	10.090
Hg(II)	25.420	12.100	5.816	0.393	0.826	1.720
Ag(I)	9.835	7.458	5.042	1.016	1.397	1.984

equations⁸. The value of ΔG is obtained from the expression $\Delta G = -RT \ln K_t$, where *K_t* is the equilibrium constant. ΔH is determined with the help of an isobar $\frac{d \ln K_t}{dt} = \frac{\Delta H}{RT^2}$ which may be written as $\frac{d \log K_t}{d(1/T)} = \frac{-\Delta H}{4.57}$. The values of log *K_t* obtained at different temperatures are plotted as a function of 1/*T*. The gradient of the tangent drawn at the point corresponding to 35° is determined and equated to $-\frac{\Delta H}{4.57}$. ΔS is then evaluated from the relation

$$\Delta S = \frac{\Delta H - \Delta G}{T}$$

The values of ΔG , ΔH and ΔS are summarised in Table 2.

TABLE 2

Thermodynamic Functions for Cu(II), Hg(II), Ag(I) complexes of ethane-1, 2-dithiol at 35°

Metal complex	ΔG (Kcal/mole)	ΔH (Kcal/mole)	ΔS (Cal/deg/mole)
Cu(II)	-10.050	-6.457	11.66
Hg(II)	-11.400	-9.997	4.55
Ag(I)	-11.100	-5.835	17.09

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